

finally with a saturated solution of NaCl. The methylene chloride was evaporated and the residue dissolved in 30 ml of benzene and kept aside for 2 hr. More dicyclohexyl urea precipitated and was filtered off. The benzene was removed at reduced pressure and the residue was crystallized from benzene-petroleum ether.

Compounds were characterized by sharp m.p.s. analysis of 'N' and I.R. (Table 1).

TABLE 1 - N-ARYL DERIVATIVES OF INDOLE-3-ACETAMIDE AND INDOLE-3-PROPIONAMIDES(I)

Compd. No. I	X	R	R ₁	n	M.P. °C	Nitrogen %	
						Calcd.	Found
a	OH	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	1	102-104	7.9	8.29
b	OH	CH ₃	CH ₃	1	92	8.29	8.08
c	OH	CH ₃	H	1	90-92	8.64	8.82
d	H	C ₂ H ₅	CH ₃	1	140	8.33	8.62
e	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	1	82	8.69	8.74
f	H	C ₂ H ₅	H	1	106	8.69	9.02
g	H	C ₂ H ₅	H	2	102	8.33	8.60
h	H	CH ₃	H	1	90	9.09	9.41
i	H	CH ₃	H	2	80	8.69	8.98

Biological activity

(a) Amoebicidal activity against *Entamoeba histolytica*²

All the nine compounds were tested against axenic culture of *E. histolytica* at a concentration of 1:8000 and were found to be devoid of amoebicidal activity.

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Synthesis of Possible Amoebicides, Part III

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SYNTHESIS of some β- and γ-(2:4-dimethoxy-5-n-alkylphenyl)-alkylamines as possible amoebicides has been described.

Synthesis of a few α-(2:4-dimethoxy-5-n-alkylphenyl)-ethylamine and its β-isomers have already been described^{1,2}. β-(2-Alkyl-4:5-dimethoxyphenyl)-ethylamine was prepared by Kachru and

Pathak³ out of which n-hexyl substituted ethylamines were found to be very active *in vitro* comparison to emetine⁴. It was, therefore, considered worthwhile to prepare similar type of compounds and to examine their amoebicidal activity. Synthesis of some γ-(2:4-dimethoxy-5-n-alkylphenyl)-propylamines (Scheme 1) and β-(2:4-dimethoxy-5-n-alkylphenyl)-ethylamines (Scheme 2) are reported in this paper.

SCHEME-1

SCHEME-2

Experimental*

2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-butylcinnamic acid (Ia): A mixture of 2:4-dimethoxy-5-n-butylbenzaldehyde (12g) malonic acid (7g), dry pyridine (75 ml) and piperidine (0.25 ml) was heated on a water bath in anhydrous conditions for 3 hr. It was then decomposed by pouring into a mixture of crushed ice and conc. HCl when a yellowish solid was obtained. It was dissolved in sodium carbonate solution and extracted with ether to remove any non-acidic material. The aqueous layer was refluxed with activated charcoal, filtered and the filtrate on acidification gave the desired acid. The acid was recrystallised from aqueous alcohol; m.p. 123°, yield, 9 g (63.1%) (Found: C, 68.25; H, 7.71. C₁₈H₂₀O₄ requires, C, 68.19; H, 7.57%). **2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-amylicinnamic acid (Ib)**, m.p. 118°, yield, 63% (Found: C, 69.20; H, 8.10. C₁₈H₂₂O₄ requires C, 69.08; H, 7.91%). **2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-hexylcinnamic acid (Ic)**, m.p. 101°, yield, 58.9% (Found: C, 70.05; H, 8.14. C₁₇H₂₈O₄ requires C, 69.85; H, 8.22%) and **2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-octylcinnamic acid (Id)**, m.p. 90°, yield, 55.8% (Found: C, 71.09; H, 8.60. C₁₆H₂₈O₄ requires C, 71.25; H, 8.75%).

β-(2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-butylphenyl)-propionic acid (IIa): Ia (11g) was dissolved in dil. NaOH and reduced with sodium amalgam (150g, 3%) in the usual manner. The alkaline liquid was decanted, refluxed with activated charcoal and filtered. The filtrate on acidification gave the desired acid which solidified on cooling. It was recrystallised from aqueous alcohol; m.p. 53°, yield, 10g (90.2%) (Found: C, 67.90; H, 8.18. C₁₈H₂₂O₄ requires C, 67.67, H, 8.27%).

β-(2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-amyphenyl)-propionic acid (IIb), m.p. 67°, yield, 90.2% (Found: C, 68.78; H, 8.53. C₁₈H₂₄O₄ requires C, 68.57; H, 8.57%). **β-(2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-hexylphenyl)-propionic acid (IIc)**, m.p. 58°, yield, 91.7% (Found: C, 69.52; H, 8.79.

* Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. Only a typical experimental procedure for each homologous series is described.

$C_{17}H_{26}O_4$ requires C, 69.39 ; H, 8.84% and β -(2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-octylphenyl)-proprionic acid (IIc), m.p. 60°, yield, 87% (Found : C, 70.54 ; H, 9.37 : $C_{18}H_{30}O_4$ requires C, 70.80 ; H, 9.32%).

β -(2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-butylphenyl)-proprionamide (IIIa) : Dry ammonia was passed through molten IIa (10g) at 190° for 2 hr. It was then poured into cold water to get the desired amide. It was recrystallised from hot water ; m.p. 115°, yield 8.5g (85.3%) (Found : N, 5.40. $C_{15}H_{22}O_3$ N requires N, 5.28%). β -(2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-amylphenyl)-proprionamide (IIIb), m.p. 107°, yield, 80.3% (Found : N, 5.21. $C_{16}H_{25}O_3$ N requires N, 5.02%), β -(2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-hexylphenyl)-proprionamide (IIIc), m.p. 105°, yield, 80.3% (Found : N, 4.67. $C_{17}H_{28}O_3$ N requires N, 4.78%) and β -(2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-octylphenyl)-proprionamide (IIId), m.p. 102°, yield 15.05% (Found : N, 4.21. $C_{19}H_{31}O_3$ N requires N, 4.36%).

γ -(2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-butylphenyl)-propylamine (IVa) : To a slurry of LAH (1g) in ether (250 ml) was added a solution of IIIa (2.1 g) in ether and worked up exactly the same way as described in our previous paper² to obtain the crystalline amine hydrochloride (EtOAc) ; m.p. 172°, yield, 1.1 g (48.3%) (Found : C, 62.22 ; H, 9.24 ; N, 5.33. $C_{15}H_{26}O_2$ NCl requires C, 62.60 ; H, 9.04 ; N, 4.87%), γ -(2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-amylphenyl)-propylamine (IVb) HCl, m.p. 168°, yield, 52.9% (Found : C, 62.89 ; H, 9.44 ; N, 4.20. $C_{16}H_{28}O_2$ NCl requires C, 63.68 ; H, 9.29 ; N, 4.64%), γ -(2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-hexylphenyl)-propylamine (IVc) HCl, m.p. 170°, yield, 18.6% (Found : C, 64.59 ; H, 9.79 ; N, 4.59. $C_{17}H_{30}O_2$ NCl requires C, 64.66 ; H, 9.51 ; N, 4.43%) and γ -(2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-octylphenyl)-propylamine (IVd) HCl, m.p. 166°, yield, 45% (Found : C, 66.73 ; H, 10.29 ; N, 3.97. $C_{19}H_{34}O_2$ NCl requires C, 66.37 ; H, 9.90 ; N, 4.04%).

2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-butylbenzaldehyde (Va) : Dry HCl gas was passed for one hr into a mixture of 2:4-dimethoxy-1-n-butylbenzene (38 g), zinc cyanide (47 g) and dry benzene (180 ml), in a three-necked flask fitted with a mercury sealed stirrer and cooled in an ice-bath. Powdered anh. $AlCl_3$ (41 g) was added gradually during 1 hr. The temperature of the bath was then raised to 60° which was maintained for 10 hr while stirring and passage of HCl gas was continued. The mass was left overnight, decomposed by ice and conc. HCl. The benzene layer was separated and the aqueous layer was extracted with benzene. The combined benzene solution was washed with water, dried over fused $CaCl_2$ and the residue after removal of benzene was distilled to give the desired aldehyde which was recrystallised from aqueous methanol ; yield, 14 g (32.2%), m.p. 47° (Found : C, 69.94 ; H, 8.34. $C_{13}H_{18}O_3$ requires C, 70.26 ; H, 8.11%), 2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-amybenzaldehyde (Vb), yield, 31.5% (Found : C, 71.30 ; H, 8.54. $C_{14}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 71.18 ; H, 8.47%), 2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-hexylbenzaldehyde (Vc), m.p. 53°, yield, 35.5% (Found : C, 72.45 ; H, 8.62. $C_{16}H_{24}O_3$ requires C, 72.00 ; H, 8.80%) and 2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-

decylbenzaldehyde (Ve), m.p. 64°, yield, 70.7% (Found : C, 74.36 ; H, 9.72. $C_{19}H_{30}O_3$ requires C, 74.50 ; H, 9.80%).

2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-butyl- β -nitrostyrene (VIa) : A solution of Va (6 g), nitromethane (4 g) and ammonium acetate (2.2 g) in acetic acid (22 ml) was refluxed under anhydrous conditions for 3hr. It was then poured into crushed ice to get yellow crystals. It was recrystallised from alcohol ; m.p. 57°, yield, 2.6 g (36.3%). (Found : C, 63.29 ; H, 7.25 ; N, 5.34. $C_{14}H_{19}O_4$ N requires C, 63.40 ; H, 7.17 ; N, 5.28%), 2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-amyl- β -nitrostyrene (VIb), m.p. 69°, yield, 33.8% (Found : C, 64.27 ; H, 7.36 ; N, 5.21. $C_{15}H_{21}O_4$ N requires C, 64.51 ; H, 7.53 ; N, 5.05%), 2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-hexyl- β -nitrostyrene (VIc), m.p. 57°, yield, 42.7% (Found : C, 65.47 ; H, 7.65 ; N, 4.52. $C_{16}H_{23}O_4$ N requires C, 65.53 ; H, 7.85 ; N, 4.78%) and 2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-decyl- β -nitrostyrene (VIe), m.p. 80°, yield, 59% (Found : C, 68.34 ; H, 8.63 ; N, 3.89. $C_{20}H_{31}O_4$ N requires C, 68.76 ; H, 8.88 ; N, 4.01%).

β -(2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-butylphenyl)-ethylamine (VIIa) : To a slurry of LAH (1.7 g) in anh. ether (190 ml) was added a solution of VIa in ether (2.4 g) at such a rate that the solvent refluxed gently. The addition was completed in half an hour and then warmed on a water-bath for 6hr and was left overnight. Excess of LAH was decomposed by dropwise addition of water and the ethereal layer was dried over solid KOH. The amine hydrochloride obtained as solid on passing dry HCl gas, was recrystallised from ethyl acetate ; m.p. 164°, yield, 0.85 g (54.8%). (Found : C, 61.07 ; H, 9.01 ; N, 5.22. $C_{14}H_{22}O_2$ NCl requires C, 61.41 ; H, 8.77 ; N, 5.12%), β -(2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-amylphenyl)-ethylamine (VIIb) HCl, m.p. 145°, yield, 48.5% (Found : C, 61.5 ; H, 9.14 ; N, 4.63. $C_{15}H_{26}O_2$ NCl requires C, 62.60 ; H, 9.04 ; N, 4.87%), β -(2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-hexylphenyl)-ethylamine (VIIc) HCl, m.p. 120°, yield, 49.9%. (Found : C, 63.51 ; H, 9.44 ; N, 4.29. $C_{16}H_{28}O_2$ NCl requires C, 63.57 ; H, 9.29 ; N, 4.64%) and β -(2:4-Dimethoxy-5-n-decylphenyl)-ethylamine (VIIe) HCl, m.p. 122°, yield, 58.6% (Found : C, 66.98 ; H, 10.44 ; N, 3.66. $C_{20}H_{36}O_2$ NCl requires C, 67.13 ; H, 10.07 ; N, 3.92%).

Pharmacological Test

Amoebicidal testing of amine hydrochlorides was undertaken at Central Durg Research Institute, Lucknow. *Entamoeba histolytica* was used as the test bacterial flora, the pH of the media being 7.2-7.4. The following data show the *in vitro* amoebicidal end point i.e. the highest dilution at which amoeba are killed.

Compound (HCl)	Amoebicidal end point
IVa	1:4,000
IVb	1:8,000
IVc	1:32,000
VIIa	1:4,000
VIIb	1:4,000
VIIc	1:16,000
VIIe	1:8,000
Emetine (Control)	1:64,000

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Partial Molal Volume of Ions in N-Methyl Acetamide Solutions

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THE ionic volume of univalent ions in water¹, formamide^{2,3}, N-methylpropionamide^{4,5}, methanol⁴, ethanol⁶, sea water⁷, dimethyl formamide⁸, ethylene glycol and formic acid⁹ are now available in the literature and the data have been employed by several workers to study interactions in solutions. Similar data in N-methylacetamide (NMA) are lacking although the apparent molal volumes of a number of uni-univalent electrolytes were reported from this laboratory¹⁰ some years ago. From the electrolyte limiting apparent molal volume data already reported¹⁰, apparent (partial) ionic volumes for common ions have been evaluated and these have been used to investigate the nature of ion-NMA interaction in solution.

Procedure: For the sake of convenience, the limiting apparent molal volume ϕ° ($\equiv \bar{V}^\circ$) values for different salts in NMA at 35° are reproduced¹⁰ in Table 1.

TABLE 1—LIMITING PARTIAL MOLAL VOLUMES $\bar{V}^\circ$ ($= \phi^\circ$) OF SOME SALTS IN NMA AT 35°C

Salt	LiCl	NaCl	NaBr	NaI	NaNO ₃	KBr	KI	KNO ₃	NH ₄ Cl	NH ₄ Br	NH ₄ I	NH ₄ NO ₃
$\bar{V}^\circ$ {cm ³ mol ⁻¹ }	20.5	26.0	32.6	42.0	35.0	40.2	45.9	42.8	35.5	44.7	51.7	47.2

The additivity law has been found to hold good for $\bar{V}^\circ$ values of electrolytes in N-methylacetamide as in other solvents^{1,3,4} and the $\bar{V}^\circ$ of salts have been divided into ionic contribution, using the method of Mukerjee¹ which assumes that for spherical, large alkali metal and halide ions, the partial molal volumes should be a smooth monotonic function of the crystallographic radius (r), quite independent of the sign of the charge. The partial molal volumes of various ions at infinite dilution are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—THE $\bar{V}^\circ_{(ion)}$ OF SOME MONOVALENT IONS IN NMA AT 35°C

Ion	Crystal radius ^a (in Å°)	$\bar{V}^\circ_{(ion)}$ (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	$\frac{\bar{V}^\circ_{(ion)}r}{z^2}$	$\frac{r^4}{z^2}$
Na ⁺	0.95	3.4	3.0	0.81
K ⁺	1.33	8.8	11.7	3.13
NH ₄ ⁺	1.60	15.4	24.6	6.55
Cl ⁻	1.81	22.4	40.5	10.73
Br ⁻	1.95	28.2	55.0	14.47
I ⁻	2.16	38.6	83.4	21.76
NO ₃ ⁻	2.03	31.9	64.8	16.98

^a—Pauling radii, Pauling, L. "The nature of the Chemical Bond", 3rd. Ed. Cornell University Press, Ithaca, N.Y. 1940.

Discussion

The limiting partial molal volume of an ion may be assumed to be the sum of two major contributions², namely, the geometric part and the electrostriction part and can be written as

$$\bar{V}^\circ_{(ion)} = \bar{V}^\circ_{(geom.)} + \bar{V}^\circ_{(elst.)} \quad (i)$$

where $\bar{V}^\circ_{(geom.)}$ takes into account the intrinsic volume of the ions plus the void space effects created on introducing the ions in the solvent and $\bar{V}^\circ_{(elst.)}$, the contribution of electrostriction due to electrostatic ion-solvent dipole interaction.

A number of relations have been proposed connecting these two effects with the radius of the ion^{11,12} these are

$$\bar{V}^\circ_{(ion)} = Ar^3 - \frac{Bz^2}{r} \quad (ii)$$

$$\bar{V}^\circ_{(ion)} = 2.52r^3 + (A-2.52)r^3 - \frac{Bz^2}{r} \quad (iii)$$

and
$$\bar{V}^\circ_{(ion)} = 2.52r^3 + A^1r^3 - \frac{B^1z^2}{r} \quad (iv)$$